

Grief through the screen: A phenomenological exploration of young adults' lived experiences of parasocial grief

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Emotional attachments to media personalities and fictional characters are a common feature of contemporary media engagement, particularly among young adults. This study examines how young adults make sense of parasocial grief following the perceived loss of a media personality or fictional character. Using a descriptive phenomenological approach, in-depth interviews were conducted with four participants aged 18 to 30 residing in Metro Manila. Analysis of the narratives revealed a patterned emotional process comprising five stages: Parasocial Belonging, Invisible String, Tear Masking, Woe Coping, and Page Turning. These stages capture the progression from emotional attachment and private mourning to coping and eventual emotional integration. While causality cannot be inferred, the findings demonstrate that parasocial loss can elicit emotionally meaningful responses that parallel recognised forms of grief. The study contributes to media psychology by clarifying parasocial grief as a distinct lived experience and underscores the importance of media literacy and psychological awareness in navigating emotionally mediated loss.

Keywords: coping strategies; emotional attachment; media literacy; parasocial grief; parasocial relationships

Media engagement increasingly extends beyond information and entertainment to the formation of emotionally meaningful bonds with fictional characters and public figures (Alavala, 2024). Through repeated exposure, audiences may develop parasocial relationships, defined as one-sided emotional attachments to media personas who remain unaware of the individual viewer (Kumar & Mathew, 2025). These relationships can foster a sense of familiarity, emotional closeness, and perceived intimacy despite the absence of reciprocal interaction or direct personal contact. Importantly, such bonds may become integrated into everyday emotional life, shaping routines, self-narratives, and coping practices in ways that resemble interpersonal relationships. Within media psychology (Dan & Erdenebold, 2024), these attachments are commonly conceptualised through parasocial interaction theory (Pimienta, 2023), which explains how repeated mediated exposure can produce experiences of perceived intimacy and emotional significance in the absence of reciprocal social exchange (Torro et al., 2022). For some individuals, the disruption or loss of a valued media figure through death, public withdrawal, or narrative closure can evoke emotional distress commonly described as parasocial grief or parasocial mourning (Akhther & Tetteh, 2023).

Media reports following the deaths of public figures such as Jonghyun in 2017, Jiah Khan in 2013, Hide in 1998, and Nill Bhattacharya in 2014 illustrate the intensity with which parasocial loss may be experienced by audiences. These cases highlight how mediated loss can trigger collective and individual expressions of mourning that extend beyond admiration into deeply personal emotional responses. In some instances, highly publicised expressions of grief have raised concerns about imitative responses among vulnerable individuals on social media, although such accounts remain descriptive rather than causal. Although these reactions often resemble recognised grief responses, including sadness, longing, and emotional disorientation, they are frequently minimised or misinterpreted because the relationship itself lacks reciprocity (Stever, 2017). The absence of social recognition may contribute to internalised shame and emotional suppression, particularly among young adults who often turn to media figures for emotional regulation, belonging, and identity affirmation (Hoelterhoff et al., 2023).

Despite growing evidence that parasocial attachments can carry significant emotional weight, parasocial grief remains underexplored as a lived emotional process, particularly within non-Western and culturally specific contexts. Existing research has tended to prioritise cognitive, behavioural, or outcome-based perspectives, often overlooking how individuals subjectively experience and make sense of such loss over time. This study addresses this gap by examining the lived experience of parasocial grief among young Filipino adults aged 18 to 30, a developmental period characterised by active identity formation and the pursuit of emotionally meaningful connections (Johnsen & Tømmeraas, 2022). Four participants were purposively selected based on their reported experience of grief following the loss of a fictional character or media personality. Consistent with qualitative research guidance, the sample size was determined by depth of engagement and data saturation rather than representativeness (Braun & Clarke, 2023; Creswell, 2013; Hennink & Kaiser, 2022).

The Philippine context provides a particularly relevant setting for this inquiry. Media consumption is deeply embedded in everyday life, with strong fan cultures, serialised storytelling, and sustained engagement with celebrities across platforms. These conditions may not only intensify parasocial attachment but also shape culturally specific expectations around emotional expression, privacy, and collective identification. Using a descriptive phenomenological approach, this study explores the behavioural, cognitive, and affective dimensions of parasocial grief through participants' narratives. Data were analysed using Colaizzi's method, with thematic structuring supported by Kelly's Repertory Grid. The study treats parasocial grieving as a legitimate emotional experience rather than a trivial or exaggerated response and considers how cultural context influences the interpretation, expression, and validation of such loss.

METHODOLOGY

Design

This study adopted a qualitative approach using a descriptive phenomenological design. Descriptive phenomenology aims to describe the essential structure of a lived experience as perceived by individuals, without imposing prior theoretical interpretation. Grounded in Husserlian philosophy, this approach focuses on participants' conscious awareness of a phenomenon and how meaning is constituted through experience. Bracketing was applied throughout the research process to suspend researcher assumptions and allow the phenomenon of parasocial grief to be described from the participants' perspectives through rich, first-person accounts.

Selection and study site

Participants were selected using purposive sampling in line with qualitative research principles that prioritise depth and relevance of experience (Creswell, 2013). Four Filipino young adults aged 18 to 30 residing in Metro Manila were recruited based on their self-reported experience of grief following the loss of a fictional character or media personality. This age range was selected due to its relevance to identity formation and emotionally significant relational engagement.

The study was conducted in Metro Manila, with participants residing in Valenzuela and Quezon City. Participants varied in age, sex, media genres typically consumed, and average daily time spent engaging with media. This variation was documented to provide contextual depth and to support interpretive understanding rather than comparative analysis.

Demographic and contextual information was collected using a Robotfoto, a structured profiling tool commonly employed in qualitative research. The Robotfoto captured age, sex, city of residence, media genres typically consumed, and average daily viewing time. The term "Robotfoto," derived from Dutch, refers to a composite participant profile designed to contextualise lived experience rather than to generate statistical comparison (De Guzman et al., 2009).

Field procedure and data collection

Participants were contacted and informed about the purpose, procedures, and ethical considerations of the study. Written informed consent was obtained prior to data collection. Semi structured interviews were conducted using an interview guide organised around broad experiential prompts aligned with the study focus. This format allowed flexibility to follow participants' narratives while ensuring coverage of key experiential domains related to parasocial attachment and loss.

Interviews were audio recorded with permission, and supplementary field notes were taken to capture contextual details and nonverbal cues. Data collection continued until thematic saturation was achieved, defined as the point at which no new experiential meanings emerged from subsequent interviews.

Mode of analysis

Interview transcripts were analysed using Colaizzi's phenomenological method (1978). This process involved repeated reading of transcripts, identification of significant statements, formulation of meanings, and clustering of these meanings into themes that reflected the psychological and

emotional dimensions of parasocial grief. Within cross case analysis was used to examine convergences and variations across participants’ accounts, allowing for a comprehensive description of the phenomenon.

Kelly’s Repertory Grid was employed as an organising framework to structure emergent stages and categories systematically. Throughout the analytic process, bracketing was maintained to minimise researcher bias, and intersubjectivity was emphasised to ensure that interpretations remained grounded in participants’ expressed meanings rather than researcher inference.

Ethical considerations

The study adhered to established ethical standards for qualitative research. Participation was voluntary, and participants were informed of their right to withdraw at any point without consequence. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained using pseudonyms and secure data storage. Screening procedures ensured participant eligibility, and all data were handled in accordance with ethical guidelines governing privacy and participant welfare.

RESULTS

The demographic profiles of the participants, including their age, preferred media genres, and the duration of their grief, are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1
 Demographic and Media Consumption Profile of Participants

Participant	Age	Genre(s) Typically Watched	Sex	Average Hours Watching	Duration of Parasocial Grief
P1	23	Crime & Mystery K-drama	F	6–7	2 days – 5 years
P2	20	K-drama & Anime	F	3	3 months
P3	19	Romance K-drama	F	3	>1 month
P4	22	Suspense/Thriller, Real-life Documentaries	M	3–5	2 days

The thematic analysis identified five distinct stages of parasocial grief, conceptualised as the P.I.T.W.P. model. These stages represent the psychological journey from the inception of a bond to the eventual resolution of loss.

Theme 1. Parasocial Belonging (Stage 1)

Parasocial belonging constitutes the initial phase where individuals identify as media enthusiasts and establish a one-sided connection with a media figure. This stage is defined by feelings of admiration and intimacy developed without direct interaction.

Media enthusiast. Participants exhibited significant engagement with various media, often utilising it as a mechanism for stress relief. P1 noted, “I’m a fangirl of K-pop idols and some Thai and Chinese actors. I feel connected and inspired by them.” P3 highlighted the habitual nature of this engagement, stating, “Addict kasi ako talaga sa mga media like sa TikTok. Ito ang comfort ko.” [“I’m really addicted to media like TikTok. It’s my comfort.”] (P3).

Intellectually engaged. For some, media consumption transitioned from passive viewing to a proactive search for knowledge. P2 reflected on this shift:

“Every day gumagamit talaga ako ng media for entertainment and awareness. Minsan, nagiging hobby ko na manood ng mga movies, film, drama, anime or etc. Every time stress ako at every time na nabo-bored ako, ginagawa ko ‘yun para ma-relax. I find it more engaging and sobrang dami kong matutunan like sa documentaries, malalaman mo kung ano yung nangyayari sa paligid natin. Kaya, ginugugol ko talaga minsan ang sarili ko sa pag-i-scroll at panonood ng kung ano-ano.” [“Every day, I really use media for entertainment and awareness. Sometimes, watching movies, films, dramas, anime, etc. becomes a hobby. Whenever I'm stressed or bored, I do that to relax. I find it more engaging, and I learn a lot, like from documentaries, you get to know what's happening around us. That's why I sometimes really immerse myself in scrolling and watching all sorts of things.”] (P2).

Emotional investment. Participants developed deep bonds when media figures mirrored their personal values. P4 mentioned, “I don't have personal ties with the media, but my late grandfather used to be an extra in some of FPJ's movies. I do know an influencer named Wish who promotes body positivity and self-importance.” (P4).

Theme 2. Invisible String (Stage 2)

The "Invisible String" refers to the intensified emotional bond where the media figure becomes personally significant to the individual despite the absence of reciprocity.

Admiration. Media personalities often serve as foundational sources of inspiration. P4 explained that “Kobe Bryant, even though I don't play basketball, taught me to keep going to school like he kept playing basketball despite his injuries. Liam, on the other hand, is symbolic to some parts of my childhood around 2014. His talents and beauty definitely inspired me a bit.” (P4).

Emotional significance. Media narratives frequently act as mirrors for the participants' own lives. P2 shared:

“They are significant to me kasi yung buhay na ipinapakita nila sa mga readers or sa mga manonood is about reality, like real life talaga. Kaya nakaka-relate talaga ako sa kanila at nagkakaroon ako ng idea sa kung paano masolusyunan ang mga problema na parehas sa problema ko. Nagkakaroon din ako ng mga idea sa past and sa mga real life situation ng mga student at nagbibigay din sila ng aral at motivation sa ‘kin, kaya sobrang mahalaga para sa ‘kin.” [“They are significant to me because the lives they show to the readers or viewers are about reality, like real life. That's why I can really relate to them, and I get ideas on how to solve problems that are similar to mine. I also gain insights about the past and real-life situations of students, and they also give lessons and motivation to me, which is why they're very important to me.”] (P2).

Deeper connection. Emotional ties are strengthened when content addresses unresolved personal issues. P3 noted, “Mahirap, sa pinapanood ko naaapektuhan ako sa *When Life Gives You Tangerines*. Ito sinusubaybayan ko ngayon. Iniisip ko nga sa sarili ko kung paano treatment ng father sa anak niya. Malaki epekto nito sa ‘kin kasi s'yempre about sa magulang.” [“It's hard, what I watch affects me, like *When Life Gives You Tangerines*. That's what I'm currently following. I start thinking about myself and how the father treats his child. It has a big impact on me because, of course, it's about parents.”] (P3).

Theme 3. Tear-Masking (Stage 3)

Tear-Masking describes the acute and often hidden emotional suffering that follows a parasocial loss.

Emotional reaction. Participants reported spontaneous physiological and emotional distress. P2 recalled, “I felt something heavy sa chest ko kaya bigla na lang bumabagsak yung luha ko... andun yung confusion and sadness na nararamdaman ko and start na ng overthinking... Parang sobrang sakit pero hindi naman sa sobrang sakit na parang namatayan ka ng kamag-anak.” [“I felt something heavy in my chest, that’s why my tears just suddenly started falling... there was confusion and sadness I was feeling, and it triggered overthinking... It was really painful, but not the kind of pain like losing a family member.”] (P2).

Prolonged emotional impact. The duration of this grief can be extensive, with P1 mentioning that the impact lasted “for two days to almost five years.” (P1).

Repeated reminders of pain. Digital triggers often renew the sense of loss. P3 observed, “Ilang days din kasi... nakikita ko sa mga edit sa TikTok... konting interaction lang na makikita mo na edit sa Facebook ganyan maaapektuhan ka talaga... Basta sobrang ganda ng series na ito pero hindi ko na kaya panoorin ulit.” [“It lasted for several days... I kept seeing edits on TikTok... even just a small interaction or edit I’d see on Facebook would really affect me... This series is really beautiful, but I just can’t watch it again.”] (P3).

Theme 4. Woe Coping (Stage 4)

Woe Coping involves the strategies used to process parasocial distress, ranging from internal reflection to selective social disclosure.

Introspection and solitude. Many participants opted for emotional seclusion and used media as private havens. P1 stated, “I have found comfort with media content, and I do sometimes feel personal reflection, pero sa fan communities minsan kasi toxic and draining.” [“I have found comfort with media content, and I do sometimes feel personal reflection, but fan communities can sometimes be toxic and draining.”] (P1). P1 further mentioned, “I divert to Watching series or reading and studying.” (P1).

Confided. Some individuals managed their sorrow by speaking with friends. P3 remarked, “Sa mga kaibigan lang na kwento ko lang sa kanya kung ano ang mga nangyayari pero hindi naman ako humanap ng professional help.” [“I only shared with my friends what was happening, but I didn’t seek professional help.”] (P3). P4 contributed, “Just by simply discussing what had occurred to them and what led to it. It wasn’t Kobe’s doing. It was the pilot’s. It wasn’t Liam’s either. It was the content.” (P4).

Theme 5. Page Turning (Stage 5)

The final stage, “Page Turning,” signifies the integration of the experience and a move towards acceptance and growth.

Manage emotions independently. The experience of parasocial grief often fostered personal resilience. P2 reflected, “I think, this taught me kung pa’no maging strong and kung paano I handle ang emotion ko ng walang tulong mula sa ibang tao. And taught me, na it’s okay to be emotional sa mga napapanood natin lalo na kapag ang bagay na iyon ay patungkol sa totoong buhay na nakakarelate ka dun.” [“I think, this taught me how to be strong and how to handle my emotions without

relying on others. And it also taught me that it's okay to be emotional about the things we watch, especially when they reflect real-life experiences that we can relate to.”] (P2). P4 added, “Since both of their deaths were during my upbringing, I guess their legacy taught me a thing or two in life.” (P4).

New perspective and emotional awareness. This process leads to a heightened understanding of one’s emotional landscape. P1 stated, “It’s change on how paano ako mag-grief.” [“It changed how I grieve.”] (P1). The participant further noted they were “learning how I grieve.” (P1). P2 observed: “I found myself na masyadong emotional sa mga fiction character at parang nagiging comfort ko sila, lalo na kapag stress, bored or pag may problem ako. Kahit na hindi s’ya totoo, at least nagbibigay ng comfort at saya sa mga tao hindi lang lungkot at galit.” [“I found myself being too emotional with fictional characters, and they have become a source of comfort for me, especially when I’m stressed, bored, or dealing with problems. Even though they aren’t real, at least they provide comfort and happiness to people, not just sadness and anger.”] (P2).

To provide a concise overview of the thematic progression identified in this study, the five stages are defined and described in Table 2.

Table 2
 5 Stages of Parasocial Grief (P.I.T.W.P)

Stage	Theme	Description
1	Parasocial Belonging	Initial admiration, emotional engagement, forming one-sided bonds
2	Invisible String	Emotional closeness despite lack of reciprocity; mediated connection
3	Tear-Masking	Deep emotional reaction, prolonged grief, hidden sorrow
4	Woe Coping	Active coping, introspection, selective social sharing, solitude
5	Page Turning	Acceptance, emotional growth, self-awareness, and moving forward

The P.I.T.W.P. model clarifies how young Filipino adults navigate the complexities of parasocial loss, illustrating a movement from initial attachment to the eventual acquisition of new emotional perspectives.

DISCUSSION

This study examined the lived experience of parasocial grief among young Filipino adults aged 18 to 30, focusing on how one-sided emotional attachments to media figures are formed, disrupted, and psychologically processed. Situated within Metro Manila, where participants reported sustained daily media engagement averaging over three hours, the findings demonstrate that parasocial loss can constitute a psychologically meaningful form of grief rather than a trivial or exaggerated emotional reaction. The P.I.T.W.P. model, comprising Parasocial Belonging, Invisible String, Tear Masking, Woe Coping, and Page Turning, offers a structured account of how parasocial grief unfolds as an experiential process rather than a single emotional response.

Conceptually, the P.I.T.W.P. framework extends existing grief models by capturing features that are specific to mediated, non-reciprocal attachments. Unlike the DABDA model of grief (Kübler-Ross, 1969), which was developed to describe responses to real life bereavement, P.I.T.W.P. reflects loss that occurs in the absence of mutual recognition, social validation, or shared mourning rituals. This distinction is critical. Participants did not merely report sadness following the loss of a media figure or fictional character, but described a complex emotional trajectory involving attachment,

concealment, coping, and eventual re integration. These findings align with previous work on parasocial breakup and parasocial loss, which has shown that the termination of mediated bonds can evoke distress patterns like those found in interpersonal loss (Cohen, 2004; Cohen & Eyal, 2006; Goulah-Pabst, 2023).

The early stages of Parasocial Belonging and Invisible String illustrate how repeated media exposure fosters perceived intimacy and emotional relevance. Consistent with Parasocial Interaction Theory (Horton & Wohl, 1956), participants described feeling connected to media figures who symbolised personal values, life aspirations, or unresolved relational themes. These attachments were strengthened by genre specific narratives such as K drama, anime, and serialised storytelling, which encourage long term emotional investment and identification. For young adults navigating identity formation and emotional regulation, such mediated figures appeared to function as stable emotional reference points, echoing developmental perspectives on attachment and meaning making in early adulthood (Erikson, 1982; Johnsen & Tømmeraas, 2022).

Tear Masking emerged as a defining feature of parasocial grief that differentiates it from socially recognised forms of bereavement. Participants frequently described concealing their distress due to fear of ridicule, minimisation, or moral judgement from others. This finding resonates with research suggesting that parasocial grief is often invalidated precisely because the relationship lacks reciprocity or social legitimacy (Steuer, 2017). The absence of socially sanctioned mourning spaces appeared to intensify internalised distress, prolong emotional processing, and contribute to isolation. Digital environments further complicated this stage, as algorithm driven content repeatedly re exposed participants to reminders of the loss, sustaining emotional activation rather than facilitating closure.

The Woe Coping stage highlights the adaptive and maladaptive strategies participants used to manage parasocial distress. Some individuals relied on introspection, selective disclosure, or immersion in alternative media content, while others avoided formal support and professional help altogether. These patterns mirror broader coping responses observed in grief research, where individuals oscillate between emotional engagement and avoidance (Mikulincer & Shaver, 2007). Importantly, coping did not necessarily involve detachment from media, but rather a renegotiation of emotional boundaries, suggesting that parasocial grief is not resolved by disengagement alone.

Page Turning, the final stage, reflects emotional integration rather than emotional erasure. Participants described increased self-awareness, emotional maturity, and a revised understanding of how media affects their inner lives. In this sense, parasocial grief functioned as a reflective process that reshaped how individuals relate to media content and to their own emotional responses. This finding supports prior research indicating that parasocial relationships can contribute to emotional resilience and meaning making, particularly when individuals are able to contextualise and interpret their experiences rather than suppress them (Kakarla & Aiswarya, 2024).

While the phenomenological design precludes causal inference, the findings suggest a meaningful association between sustained media engagement and emotionally significant grief responses. Importantly, the study also raises ethical and clinical considerations. Although not all participants experienced severe distress, the presence of prolonged grief reactions and references to suicidal ideation in extreme cases underscore the need for careful recognition of parasocial grief as a legitimate emotional experience rather than a pathological curiosity. Media related losses may act as emotional catalysts for individuals already navigating vulnerability, identity strain, or limited social support.

The findings challenge traditional assumptions within media psychology that minimise the emotional consequences of one-sided attachments. Parasocial grief, as articulated through the P.I.T.W.P. model, represents a distinct experiential process shaped by cultural context, media ecology, and developmental stage. The study therefore reinforces the importance of media literacy not only as a cognitive skill, but as an emotional competency that enables young adults to recognise, interpret, and regulate their affective investments in mediated figures.

CONCLUSION

This study documented parasocial grief as a lived emotional experience among young Filipino adults, showing that loss connected to media figures and fictional characters can carry sustained psychological meaning. Rather than presenting parasocial mourning as a fleeting reaction, the findings demonstrate that it unfolds as a process involving attachment, concealment, coping, and emotional integration. The P.I.T.W.P. framework provides a descriptive structure for this process, grounded in participants' narratives rather than imposed theoretical assumptions.

Importantly, the findings show that parasocial grief is not uniform in its outcomes. For some individuals, the experience supported reflection and emotional development, while for others it involved distress, withdrawal, or prolonged emotional impact. These differences point to the role of personal context, media engagement patterns, and emotional resources in shaping how parasocial loss is experienced and resolved. The private nature of this grief, combined with limited social recognition, emerged as a defining condition influencing how participants managed their emotions.

The study is limited by its small and gender imbalanced sample drawn from a single urban setting, which constrains broader generalisation. Future research would benefit from more diverse samples and designs that explore how parasocial grief interacts with gender, culture, and longer-term emotional adjustment. Within these limits, the study contributes a grounded account of parasocial mourning as part of contemporary emotional life and offers a framework that can inform future research, media literacy efforts, and psychological awareness around screen-based attachments.

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